

Multi-objective optimization of latent energy storage in buildings by using phase change materials with different melting temperatures

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Abstract

Technologies based on phase change materials (PCMs) are promising solutions to reduce energy consumption in buildings and related greenhouse gas emissions. However, the performance of passive PCMs in buildings is highly dependent on the melting temperatures employed, as well as the climate where the building is located. Therefore, the present contribution describes an optimization-based method to design passive latent energy storage in buildings by using PCMs with different melting temperatures. To achieve this goal, a multi-objective genetic algorithm is coupled with the building energy models developed in EnergyPlus to find the best trade-off between annual heating and cooling loads. A small office is chosen as a case study to evaluate the energy performance of the buildings incorporating the proposed PCM approach. Three different PCM layers are added to the ceilings and the external and internal walls of the building, and their parametric models are developed in EnergyPlus to optimize the melting temperature and thickness of each PCM layer simultaneously. Moreover, a method to select climate-representative locations according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 climate classification and within the WMO Region VI (Europe) is proposed and applied, resulting in eight well-representative locations. An optimization-based design is carried out for each selected location and the performances of the optimized building designs are systematically compared to the ones of the baseline models. The optimization results achieved show that regardless of the climate zone analyzed, using several PCMs with different melting temperatures instead of a single one, is preferred. Moreover, the best performance of PCMs is attained in climate zones where both the heating and cooling loads are present. In these climates, if the melting temperatures of PCMs are optimally designed, large quantities of PCMs can be incorporated into buildings without deteriorating their energy performance. However, the amount of PCMs in the internal components has to be carefully designed in hot climates, and PCMs should be placed in the envelope (inside) of buildings. Thus, the highest saving regarding the annual total loads of 11.74% is achieved in zone 5A (Cold), while the lowest one of 2.26% is obtained in zone 1B (Very hot).

Keywords: Energy-efficient building, Latent energy storage, Phase change material, Multiple

1. Introduction

European Union (EU) has set progressive goals to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and achieve different energy and climate targets [1]. The most ambitious EU strategy is the European Green Deal [2], which plans to realize net-zero greenhouse gas emissions by 2050, decoupled from the economic growth and resource demands in the EU. This and other EU strategies are aligned to comply with the climate goals released by the Paris agreement [3], which aims to limit global warming to well below 2 °C, preferably to 1.5 °C, compared to pre-industrial levels. Within this context, buildings are a key sector in the EU since they represent approximately 40% of total energy consumption, 36% of associated CO₂ emissions, and 55% of electricity consumption [4]. For this reason, energy-efficient buildings such as nearly zero energy buildings (NZEBs) are part of the central core of the EU policy [5]. Thus, the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD-2010/31/EU [6]) stated that “Member States shall ensure that by 31 December 2020, all new buildings should be nearly zero-energy buildings; and since 31 December 2018, all new buildings occupied and owned by public authorities should be nearly zero-energy buildings”.

Latent heat storage (LHS) is a technique that is increasingly employed as a solution to reduce energy consumption in buildings. Furthermore, phase change materials (PCMs) are the main candidate to develop different technologies based on the LHS concept. Compared to the sensible-heat-based solutions, PCMs have a higher storage density. This is, large amounts of heat can be stored in small PCM volumes [7].

1.1. PCMs in buildings

PCMs can store and release large amounts of heat throughout their phase transitions, which are usually solid-liquid and liquid-solid, respectively. These phase transitions occur within an almost constant temperature range, which is commonly referred to as the melting temperature. Thus, exploiting this physical phenomenon, PCMs can be incorporated into building components for reducing cooling [8, 9] and heating [10] loads, for achieving a stabilizing thermal effect in indoor spaces [11], and for enhancing the energy performance of buildings [12].

To achieve a successful performance of passive PCMs in buildings, a proper design of their thermophysical properties, their quantities, and their locations are required [13, 14]. Within this context, several efforts have been made to understand and quantify the influence of different design parameters of PCMs. Using a parametric analysis, Ascione et al. [15] studied the proper PCM position as one of the passive strategies to achieve nearly zero-energy buildings in Mediterranean climates. They concluded that using a PCM melting temperature of 25 °C on the inner side is recommended, and this can achieve reductions in cooling energy demand from 2% (in Madrid) to 13% (in Naples). Saffari et al. [16] performed a simulation-based optimization analysis of PCM

melting temperature to improve the energy performance in buildings across different climates according to the Köppen-Geiger climate classification. By applying this method, they demonstrated that the optimal selection of the PCM melting temperature can highly influence the total energy consumption of a building, and this strongly depends on the considered climatic conditions. The results also showed that an increment in the PCM quantity can either increase or decrease the performance of the PCMs significantly, and so their benefits.

Recently, Kishore et al. [17] performed a parametric and sensitivity analysis for several PCM design parameters to achieve an optimal thermal load modulation in lightweight buildings. From the analyses, the authors concluded that the best PCM location was nearest to the interior of the building, while PCM melting temperatures of 24-25 °C were optimal for both locations studied (Phoenix and Las Vegas). Moreover, using parametric analysis, the authors showed that PCM melting temperature was the strongest parameter affecting thermal load modulation, followed by PCM location and PCM thickness.

The fact that melting temperature is the most important design parameter is because this is directly related to the effectiveness of passive PCMs in buildings. Thus, the proper PCM melting temperature depends on both the heating and cooling loads of the building, which in turn depends on the design and typology of the building and the local weather conditions. If the melting temperature is designed for only one load/season (heating or cooling), PCMs may not have sufficient benefits for the entire year or, even worse, they may generate undesired thermal effects. Therefore, because of the complexity of designing and optimizing building-embedded PCMs incorporated in buildings, the use of advanced design methods such as building performance simulation (BPS) tools is highly recommended [14].

With a closer relationship to the aim of the current work, some authors have suggested employing more than one PCM with different melting temperatures in a building to improve the performance of the PCMs for all seasons of the year. Among recent efforts, Kheradmand et al. [18] proposed an experimental evaluation of a hybrid PCM-based mortar that combines three microencapsulated PCMs with melting temperatures of 10 °C, 26 °C, and 28 °C, respectively. The mass of PCMs for the mortar composite was the same for each PCM type and equivalent to 6.12% of the total weight of the mortar. Two small-scale prototypes using a reference mortar (without PCM) and the proposed hybrid PCM-based mortar were tested experimentally. These prototypes were exposed to thermal boundary conditions artificially generated while aiming to emulate realistic summer and winter weather scenarios (two days) of Portugal's climate. The experimental results showed that the prototype using the hybrid PCM-based mortar has an improved capacity to attenuate daily environmental thermal amplitudes in the test cells for both summer and winter scenarios compared to the prototype employing the reference mortar. The main drawback of this research, which was also highlighted by the authors themselves, is the unrealistic conditions of the prototypes compared to actual buildings. Another limitation of the methodology is its inability to design and optimize the melting temperatures and quantities of PCMs.

Recently, Berardi and Soudian [19] performed an experimental investigation of latent heat thermal storage using PCMs with different melting temperatures for building energy retrofitting in Canada. In this work, the authors proposed a composite PCM system, which comprises two commercially available PCM products with melting temperatures of 21.7 °C and 25 °C, respectively. Similar to in [18], two cells were built at a small scale to perform the experiments, in which one included the hybrid PCM composite on the walls and ceiling, and the other one acted as the baseline model. The temperatures on the surfaces and indoors were measured while the prototypes were exposed to real external weather between July to October in Toronto, Canada. The experimental results showed that the prototype using the hybrid PCM composite can achieve an improved stabilizing thermal effect for the analyzed temperatures compared to the baseline model. Another interesting finding of this work was the sensitivity and influence showed by the PCMs on the ceiling compared to the ones on the walls, i.e. these PCMs demonstrated a higher percentage of heat absorption and reduction of the high peak temperatures. Although this work presented a consistent methodology, it has some limitations regarding the generalization of results and conclusions. The PCM melting temperatures were proposed a priori, which prevents the capability to design and optimize them. Furthermore, the conclusions are still constrained to the simplifications of the experiments, i.e., the results are obtained from a prototype without air-conditioning and internal gains, and for non-representative climate conditions (i.e., a short period of experiments and only one climate region). These restrictions limit the understanding of the real benefits of including different PCMs with more than one melting temperature in actual buildings.

1.2. Optimal melting temperatures of PCMs in buildings

As introduced before, PCM melting temperature is the most influential design parameter of PCMs to improve their passive performances in buildings. Furthermore, the literature research has studied the relationship between the PCM melting temperature and the reduction of both heating and cooling loads in buildings. However, most of the works analyzed this implicitly or separately. For example, Saffari et al. [16] studied the optimal PCM melting temperature to improve the energy performance of buildings for different climate regions according to the Köppen-Geiger classification, but they only optimized the annual total loads. Thus, in some cases, no clear relationships between the PCM melting temperatures and the heating/cooling energy savings could be derived. Moreover, Arıcı et al. [20] found results indicating that the optimal PCM melting temperature is different for each month/season of the year, which implicitly indicates the benefits of using several PCM melting temperatures in a building. A few research studied the optimal design of PCM melting temperatures as a multi-objective problem for heating and cooling loads in buildings [21, 22].

Fig. 1 shows conceptual results for an optimal design of PCM melting temperatures as a multi-objective problem between the heating and cooling loads in air-conditioned buildings. As can be seen in Fig. 1a, the solution of the optimal design of the PCM melting temperature is not unique,

but a set of optimal solutions. Thus, there are optimal designs that can easily reduce the heating loads than the cooling ones and vice versa.

To better understand the physical reasons for the conflicting relationship between the heating and cooling loads regarding the PCM melting temperatures, Fig. 1b shows the description of the performance of the optimal designs regarding the melting temperature and its relationship with the thermostat setpoints of the HVAC system. As a general rule, if the building conditions mentioned before are present, all the optimal PCM melting temperatures will be almost within the range of the setpoint temperatures. Thus, the best heating design is obtained with a low melting temperature within the range of control, i.e. a temperature nearby the setpoint of heating. This is because, during the cold season, the PCM has to maximize the probability of storing the extra heat and releasing it again into the indoor air when the temperature tries to decrease, and so reducing the energy required for heating. If a high PCM melting temperature is chosen (e.g., nearby the setpoint of cooling), this PCM will have less extra energy to store, and the PCM effectiveness will quickly decrease during the cold season. Thus, the optimal PCM melting temperature for reducing the heating loads is nearby the HVAC setpoint of heating. Regarding the optimal PCM melting temperature for cooling, occurs something similar but oppositely. This means that the optimal PCM melting temperature for reducing the cooling loads is the same value (or slightly higher) as the HVAC setpoint of cooling. By using this melting temperature, the optimal design also tries to maximize the PCM effectiveness between a compromise in reducing the cooling loads and the daily release of the stored heat to be available the next day. This is, a PCM with the same storage capacity and a lower melting temperature has the same storing capacity to reduce the cooling loads, but its probability to achieve a complete daily cycle is lower during hot seasons.

Therefore, based on these physical observations, a combination of PCMs with different melting temperatures is expected to perform better to simultaneously reduce both heating and cooling loads for real climatic conditions throughout the whole year.

Fig. 1: Conceptual scheme regarding the optimal PCM melting temperature in buildings. (a) Pareto front between annual heating and cooling loads. (b) Relationship between the optimal PCM melting temperatures and the annual heating and cooling loads of the building.

1.3. Research aims and contributions

The present work aims to introduce a novel optimization-based method to design passive latent energy storage using phase change materials with different melting temperatures in buildings. To achieve this goal, a multi-objective genetic algorithm is dynamically coupled with the building energy model developed in EnergyPlus to find the best trade-off between the annual heating and cooling loads. As a case study building, the small office from the prototype models of the U.S. Department of Energy (DOE) with the ASHRAE Standard 90.1–2019 is chosen. Three different PCMs are added to the ceiling and external and internal walls in the building. Parametric models of the PCMs are developed in EnergyPlus to simultaneously optimize the melting temperature and quantity of each PCM. To evaluate the energy performance of the buildings employing the proposed PCM approach in different climates, eight climate-representative locations within the WMO Region VI (Europe) are selected according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 climate classification. Finally, an optimization-based design is performed for each selected location, and the performances of the optimized designs are exhaustively compared regarding the baseline building models.

2. Methods

2.1. Selection of climate-representative locations within the WMO Region VI (Europe)

Climate classification is useful for the design of various energy systems since within each climatic zone/region the performance of the system can be assumed to suffer small variations, which facilitates the draw of design guidelines and standardizations. Regarding building design, the Köppen-Geiger climate classification [23] had been widely employed by researchers and professionals over years. However, this climatic zoning was developed for general purposes considering only the weather aspects, which decreases its usability for building energy applications [24]. For example, it was recently demonstrated that this zoning can be overlapped up to 37% when it is validated using building energy performance data [25]. To address these limitations, new performance-based climate classifications are being developed for building energy applications [26]. Although performance-based classification has been demonstrated to be more accurate, currently, there is not a global classification or general method to apply. Regarding European climates, some efforts had been made in this line [27], but the classification obtained still does not perform accurately for cooling energy demand [28]. Among the existing climate classifications, the ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification [29] is the most adequate for building energy applications [25]. Thus, this climatic zoning is adopted for the current research.

The ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification is based on two main indexes: the cooling degree-day base 10 °C (CDD10), and the heating degree-day base 18 °C (HDD18). By using these indicators and their corresponding criteria limits, eight main climate zones can be derived as shown in Table 1. Fig. 2 shows the world map according to ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification, as well as the six WMO Regions.

Therefore, a selection of climate-representative locations according to the ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification is carried out to investigate the performance of the PCM approach proposed in this work regarding the different climates across Europe. To this end, all the locations that are classified in the ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 and located within the WMO Region VI (Europe), and have a climate weather file in the EnergyPlus format (EPW) for building performance simulation in the repository *Climate.OneBuilding* [30] are assessed aiming to select one representative location for each climate zone. Thus, for each zone/sub-zone of the ASHRAE Standard 169-2020, the nearest location to the zone “centroid” is selected. The centroid is determined according to the CDD10 and HDD18 criteria shown in Table 1. For zones 0 and 8, the CDD10 and HDD18 values that define the centroid are determined as the mean value for the available locations. By this approach, locations with well-representative climatic conditions are selected avoiding those locations close to the border of the zones that can be misclassified.

Table 1: Climate zones according to the ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification [29].

Climate zone (ASHRAE 169)	Climate description	Criteria - CDD10 [°C], HDD18 [°C]
0	Extremely Hot	$6000 < \text{CDD10}$
1	Very Hot	$5000 < \text{CDD10} \leq 6000$
2	Hot	$3500 < \text{CDD10} \leq 5000$
3	Warm	$\text{CDD10} \leq 3500 \ \& \ \text{HDD18} \leq 2000$
4	Mixed	$\text{CDD10} \leq 3500 \ \& \ 2000 < \text{HDD18} < 3000$
5	Cool	$\text{CDD10} \leq 3500 \ \& \ 3000 < \text{HDD18} < 4000$
6	Cool	$4000 < \text{HDD18} \leq 5000$
7	Very Cold	$5000 < \text{HDD18} \leq 7000$
8	Subarctic/Arctic	$7000 < \text{HDD18}$

Fig. 2: World map of climate zones according to ASHRAE Standard 169-2020 classification and six WMO Regions. Source: modified from [29].

2.2. Case study building

The small office of the prototype building models of the DOE with the ASHRAE Standard 90.1–2019 is chosen as a case study building [31]. The DOE Prototype Building Models were developed by Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), under contract with the DOE. These building models were derived from DOE’s Commercial Reference Building Models with modifications based on input from the ASHRAE Standard 90.1 committee, the Advanced Energy Design Guide series, and building industry experts. The prototype models are high-performance building designs that were developed to quantify energy-saving impacts from newly published editions of ASHRAE Standard 90.1, 189.1, IECC, and other energy codes and standards.

The prototype model chosen for this research is a commercial building with a total area of 511.16 m². This building comprises four perimeter thermal zones, one core zone, and one attic zone, see Fig. 3a. To separate from the particular performance of the original systems for air-conditioning, they are removed and replaced by ideal HVAC systems. The thermostat control is set constant to 18°C for heating and 26°C for cooling, and is available during occupied hours. This range of thermostat control is employed for all climate zones. Note that it was widened compared to the original one to better research the optimal PCM melting temperatures. By this approach, the heating and cooling performance of the building is measured independently on the equipment installed for the air-conditioning. The remaining configuration of the model (internal loads, occupant, schedules, etc.) is kept as the original. These models are implemented in the software EnergyPlus [32] - version 9.

Fig. 3: Small office selected from the prototype building models of the DOE [31] and employed herein as the case study building. (a) General thermal zone configuration. (b) Detailed wall and roof configurations.

Table 2 summarizes the main characteristics of the energy model for the office building. A few features of the prototypes are modified according to ASHRAE Standard 90.1-2019 for each climate zone, which results in a different model for each one. These features are mainly related to the thermal properties of the envelope as shown in Table 3. Therefore, the original models with the modifications herein proposed, but without incorporating PCMs into the building, are henceforth denominated as “baseline” models. For further information about the detailed configuration of the EnergyPlus models, see [33, 34] or the EnergyPlus input data files (IDF) that are available as supplementary research data.

Table 2: Details of the main model configurations for the small office building.

Item		Descriptions
Building Typology		Office
Building Prototype		Small Office
Total Floor Area [m ²]		511.16
Aspect Ratio		1.5
Number of Floors		1
Window-to-Wall Ratio [%]		24.4 for South and 19.8 for the other three orientations
Floor to ceiling height [m]		3.048
HVAC system		
Type	Heating type	Ideal loads
	Cooling type	
Thermostat Setpoint [°C]	Cooling	18
	Heating	26
Internal Loads		
Lighting	Average power density [W/m ²]	6.89
Plug load	Average power density [W/m ²]	6.78
Occupancy	Area weighted average [m ² /person]	16.59
	Total number of People	31

Table 3: Main envelope properties for the building models according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 climate zone.

Climate Zone	Envelope properties						
	Roof		Wall		Glazing		
	Solar absorptance [-]	U-factor [W/m ² -K]	Solar absorptance [-]	U-factor [W/m ² -K]	Window U-factor [W/m ² -K]	Solar Heat Gain Coeff. [-]	Visible Transmittance [-]
Zone 0	0.700	0.153	0.700	0.505	2.839	0.230	0.253
Zone 1	0.700	0.153	0.700	0.505	2.839	0.230	0.253
Zone 2	0.700	0.153	0.700	0.505	2.612	0.250	0.275
Zone 3	0.700	0.153	0.700	0.505	2.385	0.250	0.275
Zone 4	0.700	0.119	0.700	0.363	2.044	0.360	0.396
Zone 5	0.700	0.119	0.700	0.290	2.044	0.380	0.418
Zone 6	0.700	0.119	0.700	0.290	1.931	0.380	0.418
Zone 7	0.700	0.097	0.700	0.290	1.647	0.400	0.440
Zone 8	0.700	0.097	0.700	0.182	1.476	0.400	0.440

2.3. PCM approach and design variables

Fig. 3b shows the PCM configuration approach proposed for the current research. This comprises the incorporation of three different PCM layers: between the gypsum boards for the internal walls, and between the gypsum boards and the insulation layers for the ceilings and external walls. To study the potential of PCMs with different melting temperatures in the same building, the melting temperature of the three PCMs can vary independently. Moreover, the thickness of the three PCM layers can also vary independently. By this simultaneous optimization, the optimal

melting temperature and amount of each PCM are studied, as well as the optimal placement of the PCM. This latter can be implicitly derived from the optimal thickness because the PCMs are proposed to be placed in well-differentiated thermal conditions as are the ceilings, and the external and internal walls.

To evaluate the performance of an actual PCM, the Rubitherm RT25HC [35] is chosen as the reference PCM, which is a commercially available PCM product. The melting temperature of the PCMs is characterized by the peak melting temperature (T_{peak}), which represents the temperature where the PCM reaches the maximum thermal capacity. Fig. 4 shows the enthalpy-temperature ($h - T$) curve of the RT25HC, which has a T_{peak} of 25 °C (green central curve). The RT25HC has a thermal conductivity of 0.2 W/(m-K), a density of 880 kg/m³, and a specific heat capacity (sensible) of 2000 J/(kg-K).

Fig. 4: Enthalpy curve of the PCM employed (RT25HC [35]) and the optimization range allowed based on a shift of the experimental curve, which is characterized through the T_{peak} .

PCM modeling. The latent thermal capacity of PCMs is represented by the PCM model (MaterialProperty:PhaseChange) of EnergyPlus. The accuracy of this model has been widely validated regarding experimental results, and analytical solutions [36, 37]. The main input required for the model is the $h - T$ curve of PCMs, which can be described by up to 16 points of data. Thus, the model iteratively employs this information to calculate the thermal capacity property of PCMs at each time step as:

$$c_p(T) = \frac{h_i^j - h_i^{j-1}}{T_i^j - T_i^{j-1}}, \quad (1)$$

where h is the enthalpy (J/kg), T is the temperature (°C), i indicates the node, and the j and $j - 1$ refer to the current and previous time steps, respectively. To simulate PCMs with EnergyPlus, the conduction finite difference (CondFD) solution algorithm is employed along with 30 time-steps per hour to guarantee accurate results, as recommended in [36].

PCM design variables. Table 4 summarizes the design variables and their lower (x^L) and upper (x^U) domain limits. As introduced before, the PCM melting temperature characterized by the T_{peak} and the PCM layer thickness, are simultaneously optimized for each of the three PCM layers. To this, three separated PCM models are developed in EnergyPlus, as described in the previous paragraphs. To study the optimal melting temperature of each PCM, the models are parameterized through a numerical shift for the temperature (T) of the original h-T curve, see Fig. 4. The range allowed for the variation of the T_{peak} is the same that the dual setpoint thermostat configured in the ideal HVAC system, within 18-26 °C. The thicknesses of the PCM layers also are parametrized to allow their variation within the ranges shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Design variables and their optimization ranges.

Design variable	x^L	x^U
T_{peak} PCM-1 [°C]	18	26
T_{peak} PCM-2 [°C]	18	26
T_{peak} PCM-3 [°C]	18	26
Thickness PCM-1 [m]	0.001	0.025
Thickness PCM-2 [m]	0.001	0.025
Thickness PCM-3 [m]	0.001	0.025

2.4. Multi-objective optimization

As shown in [21, 22], the heating and cooling performances of a building conflict with each other regarding the optimal design of the PCM melting temperatures. Thus, the solution of the optimal design of the PCM melting temperature is not unique, but a set of non-dominated solutions, which is commonly called as Pareto front [38]. A solution is defined as non-dominated (i.e., Pareto-optimal) whether there is not any other feasible solution that improves one objective without deteriorating at least one another.

Therefore, a multi-objective optimization approach is proposed to find the optimal set of parameters defining the PCM layers that improve both, the heating and cooling performances, of buildings. This can be mathematically described by the following unconstrained bi-objective optimization problem:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{\mathbf{x} \in \mathcal{V}} && [f_1(\mathbf{x}), f_2(\mathbf{x})] \\
 & \text{subject to :} && (2) \\
 & && x_i^L \leq x_i \leq x_i^U, \quad i = 1, \dots, n;
 \end{aligned}$$

where x_i^L and x_i^U are the lower and upper limits for the corresponding design variable x_i , see Table 4 in Section 2.3. The objective functions $f_1(\mathbf{x})$ and $f_2(\mathbf{x})$ are the annual heating and cooling loads, which are obtained from the results for each EnergyPlus simulation.

To solve the unconstrained optimization problem (2), the multi-objective Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) [39] is dynamically coupled with the EnergyPlus simulations. The decision for choosing the NSGA-II is because of its capability to achieve a wide diversity of optimal solutions along the Pareto front. This capability is essential herein for investigating the relationships between the optimal design parameters defining each PCM layer and the performance of the buildings incorporating them.

Therefore, during the optimization process, at each fitness evaluation step, the two objective functions (i.e., the annual heating and cooling loads) are computed for each individual in the population via an EnergyPlus simulation. This means that the models for each PCM layer are dynamically set according to the design variables (i.e., the melting temperatures and thickness) that are proposed by the optimization algorithm. This procedure continues until it reaches the stopping criterion, which herein is the total number of generations.

The optimization method proposed is programmed in the Python language. To this, the platform Distributed Evolutionary Algorithms in Python (DEAP) [40] is employed for implementing the NSGA-II. Moreover, the coupling with EnergyPlus is based on our previous development [41], which was recently updated to optimize PCMs [22].

The NSGA-II settings for solving the optimization problems in each climate zone are detailed in Table 5. Thus, 48 individuals are employed as the population size to achieve good diversity of solutions along the Pareto front [39], and 120 generations are used to guarantee converged results [42]. By employing this configuration, around 5700 EnergyPlus simulations are run in each optimization-based design.

Table 5: Settings of the NSGA-II for performing the optimization of the case studies.

Item	Value
Population size	48
Number of generations	120
Selection	Tournament
Crossover method	Blended method
Crossover probability	90%
Mutation method	Gaussian
Mutation probability	0.2%

3. Results

This section presents and discusses the results obtained in the present research. The climatic representative locations according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 that are selected in Europe are presented in Section 3.1. The performances of the baseline buildings for each representative climate are detailed in Section 3.2.

3.1. Climate-representative locations within the WMO Region VI (Europe)

The distribution obtained for the locations analyzed is shown in Fig. 5. Thus, 1817 locations meet the three proposed criteria: i) be classified in ASHRAE Standard 169-2020, ii) be located

in the WMO Region VI (Europe), and iii) have an EPW file for performing building energy simulations using EnergyPlus. Locations are in all the main climate zones, except for zone 0 (Extremely Hot). Moreover, most of the locations (609) are in zone 5A, followed by zones 4A (392), 6A (269), 7 (226), and 3A (183). This distribution is because of the geographic extension of each zone but also is related to the population located in the zones. Because there are sub-zones with no locations (i.e., zones 6B, 5B, 1A, 0A, and 0B), 14 climate-representative locations are finally selected. For research purposes, only one location for each main climate zone is employed, resulting in eight selected locations. The complete list of the selected locations can be found as research data in [43].

Fig. 5: Distribution of the analyzed locations according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 climate classification and within the WMO Region VI (Europe).

Table 6 summarizes the main information for the selected climate-representative locations. Thus, to evaluate the performance of the buildings for the current climate of each selected location, the recent typical meteorological years (TMYx.2007-2021) are employed. These climate data are available in the repository *Climate.OneBuilding* [30].

Table 6: Selected climate-representative locations according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 classification and within the WMO Region VI (Europe).

Climate zone (ASHRAE 169)	Selected location	Latitude	Longitude	Elevation [m]	WMO ID	CDD10 [°C]	HDD18 [°C]
1B	Aqaba (Jordan)	N 29° 36.72'	E 35° 1.08'	53	403400	5597	162
2A	Beirut (Lebanon)	N 33° 49.26'	E 35° 29.28'	27	401000	4217	319
3A	Capo Pertusato (France)	N 41° 22.48'	E 9° 10.70'	116	77700	2464	1116
4A	Osijek (Croatia)	N 45° 27.78'	E 18° 48.60'	88	142840	1964	2502
5A	Torun (Poland)	N 53° 3.00'	E 18° 34.98'	72	122500	1027	3499
6A	Kongsvinger (Norway)	N 60° 11.42'	E 12° 0.40'	148	14680	614	4498
7	Hovden (Norway)	N 59° 34.60'	E 7° 23.38'	836	14410	127	6005
8	Qaanaaq (Greenland)	N 77° 29.10'	W 69° 22.38'	16	42050	7	9676

3.2. Performance of the baseline buildings in the climate-representative locations

Fig. 6 shows the annual heating, cooling, and total (heating+cooling) loads obtained for the baseline buildings in the selected climate-representative locations. The first observation is the high performance of the baseline buildings for all the analyzed climate zones. This is, the annual total loads are between 20-30 kWh/m² for climate zones 3A, 4A, 5A, 6A, and 7 climate zones; approximately 50 kWh/m² for zones 2A and 8, and 70 kWh/m² for zone 1B. Regarding the cooling loads, they monotonically decrease from climate zone 1B to 7 and slightly increase in zone 8. This latter behavior is because the configuration of the baseline buildings is different in climate zones 7 and 8, see Table 3. Regarding the heating loads, they monotonically increase from zone 2A (only 0.0005 kWh/m²) to 8, and no heating loads are obtained for the climate zones 1A and 2A. Because of the typology of the studied building (office), the loads are dominant cooling in general terms.

Fig. 6: Annual heating, cooling, and total loads for the baseline models in the climate-representative locations selected.

3.3. Optimization results

This section presents and discusses the optimization results obtained for the proposed PCM approach in the different climate zones. For a better interpretation of the coming results, Fig. 7 shows a conceptual scheme of the bi-objective optimization results for the proposed problem, i.e., minimizing the annual heating and cooling loads of the office buildings. The horizontal axis represents the annual heating loads, and the vertical axis represents the cooling ones. Thus, 48 optimized designs are obtained after each optimization process on the Pareto front between the annual heating and cooling loads. The first optimized design, named Opt-1, corresponds to the best PCM design to reduce the heating loads; while the latest design, named Opt-48, represents the best PCM design to minimize the annual cooling loads. Moreover, depending on the load dominance, the best design for reducing the annual total loads can be an intermediate solution or one of the extreme solutions of the Pareto front, i.e., Opt-1 or Opt-48.

The optimization results obtained for climate zones 1B, 2A, 3A, and 4A are shown in Fig. 8. For example, Fig. 8a-c show the results for the climate zone 1B. Particularly, the values of the objective

Fig. 7: References of the bi-objective optimization results for their better interpretation.

functions for the optimized designs and the feasible designs analyzed during the optimization are depicted in Fig. 8a; the optimal peak melting temperatures (T_{peak}) of PCMs are shown in Fig. 8b, and the corresponding optimum thicknesses of the PCM layers are plotted in Fig. 8c. As anticipated by the results for the baseline model, the building has no loads for heating in this climate zone, and they are also not generated by the incorporation of PCMs into the building. Thus, for this case, the bi-objective design space collapse into a one-dimensional space, and the expected “Pareto front” collapse into a unique optimal design. Even with one of the objective functions equal to zero, the optimization by the NSGA-II works properly and the design of the PCMs can be carried out robustly. Regarding the performance of the designs incorporating PCMs into the building, all the feasible solutions improve the cooling performance of the building compared to the baseline design. The optimal design of the PCMs indicates that a $T_{\text{peak}} = 25.6$ °C is preferred for the PCM-1, a $T_{\text{peak}} = 25.4$ °C for the PCM-2, and a $T_{\text{peak}} = 25$ °C for the PCM-3. Note that for this climate the optimal melting temperatures of PCMs are similar and with high values because of the full dominance of the cooling loads. However, the optimal design combines 25 mm of thickness for the PCM-1 and PCM-3 with 12.54 mm for the PCM-2, which indicates that is not beneficial to add more PCM to the internal walls in this climate. A similar pattern to these results is observed for climate 2A, see Figs. 8d-f. The incorporation of the PCMs improves the performance of all the feasible designs compared to the baseline model. For most of the feasible designs, the small annual heating loads of the baseline model are eliminated with the PCMs and again a unique solution is found instead of a Pareto front. The optimal T_{peak} is 25.7 °C, 25.6 °C, and 25 °C for the PCM-1, PCM-2, and PCM-3, respectively. In this climate, the thicknesses of the PCM-1 and PCM-3 are also 25 mm, but 5.2 mm is preferred for the PCM-2.

Regarding climate 3A, the design space already shows contradictory solutions between heating and cooling loads, and a Pareto front is obtained, see Fig. 8g. All the designs that incorporate optimum PCMs (i.e., on the Pareto front) improve both the heating and cooling performances compared to the baseline model, and most of them can reduce to zero the small annual loads of the baseline model. In this case, Figs. 8h-i show the optimal melting temperatures and thicknesses of PCMs along the Pareto front, respectively, following from the best heating design (Opt-1) up to

the best cooling design (Opt-48). Regarding the optimal PCM melting temperatures, they have a generally increased tendency of the values from Opt-1 until Opt-48, showing similar values for the PCM-2 and PCM-3, and notably different values for the PCM-1 (external walls). For reducing the heating loads (Opt-1), the PCM-1 selects a T_{peak} around 18 °C, while PCM-2 and PCM-3 prefer values around 22 °C. For reducing the cooling loads (Opt-48), the PCMs employ melting temperatures of 26 °C, 24.1 °C, and 25.2 °C for the PCM-1, PCM-2, and PCM-3, respectively. As to the optimal PCM thicknesses, the PCM-1 and PCM-3 employ the maximum allowed (25 mm) for all the solutions, while the PCM-2 employs 25 mm for the solutions that better work to reduce the heating loads (Opt-1 to Opt-21); then, lower thicknesses are preferred in this layer for reducing the cooling loads of the building.

Figs. 8j-l show the optimization results for climate 4A. In this climate, the heating loads are already notable and the design space between the annual heating and cooling loads is complex, it is a non-convex and has discontinuities. All the feasible designs, including those that incorporate optimum PCMs (i.e., on the Pareto front), improve both the heating and cooling performance compared to the baseline model. Moreover, all the optimum designs on the Pareto front employ a thickness layer of 25 mm (maximum allowed) combined with specific melting temperatures for each PCM layer, see Figs. 8k-l. For reducing the heating loads (Opt-1), the PCM-1 selects a T_{peak} of 18 °C, while PCM-2 and PCM-3 prefer values of 19.1 °C and 20.4 °C. After that, the melting temperatures have an increased tendency of the values along the design on the Pareto front, but with specific values for each one. For reducing the cooling loads (Opt-48), the PCMs employ melting temperatures of 24 °C, 24.2 °C, and 25 °C for the PCM-1, PCM-2, and PCM-3, respectively.

The optimization results obtained for the climate zones 5A, 6A, 7, and 8 are shown in Fig. 9. Regarding the design spaces, they became wider because of the presence of both the heating and cooling loads. This tendency is clear if the design spaces are compared to each other for the different climate zones; i.e., the more balance between heating and cooling loads, the wider the design space. For these climate regions, all the designs that incorporate optimum PCMs (i.e., on the Pareto front), improve both the heating and cooling performances compared to the baseline model. However, feasible designs can worsen the heating performance of the building compared to the baseline model, and the probability of this increase if the heating loads are dominant, see Fig. 9a, Fig. 9d, Fig. 9g, and Fig. 9j. The optimal thicknesses of PCM layers are 25 mm (maximum allowed) for all cases. Regarding the optimal melting temperatures, the PCM-1 (external walls) preferred lower and well different values than the other PCMs for climate 5A. Note that this behavior is observed for climates where the annual heating loads are appreciable, but they are still lower than the cooling ones (e.g., climate zones 3A, 4A, and 5A). For climate zones where the heating loads are dominant (i.e., climate zones 6A, 7, and 8), the melting temperatures for the PCM-3 are the lower ones, followed by the PCM-1 and PCM-2, respectively. In general, the PCM melting temperatures have also an increased tendency of their values along the Pareto front, i.e.,

Fig. 8: Optimization results obtained for climate zones 1B, 2A, 3A, and 4A.

from the best heating design (Opt-1) to the best cooling design (Opt-48). However, all the optimal melting temperatures are equal to or higher than 20 °C for climate zones where the heating loads

are dominant (e.g., climate zones 6A, 7, and 8).

Fig. 9: Optimization results obtained for climate zones 5A, 6A, 7, and 8.

3.4. Analysis of the annual loads

In this section, an analysis of the annual load savings for the buildings using the optimal PCMs compared to the baseline models is carried out for the different climate zones. For this, the designs on the Pareto front that minimize the total loads (i.e., min (heating + cooling)) are selected, and their performance is compared to the baseline model. The results of this analysis are shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10a shows the differences in the annual total loads between the optimized designs and their corresponding baseline models for each climate zone analyzed. The optimal PCMs can reduce the annual total loads by 1.53-2.75 kWh/m² compared to the baseline models. Moreover, the performances of the optimal PCMs are similar in several zones, except for climates 4A and 5A, where the PCMs achieve large total load savings. Thus, optimal PCMs attain the best performances in climate regions where both loads are present. Conversely, the performances of PCMs worsen in climate regions where one of the load types is dominant. This latter is highly noticeable for climate regions with a dominance of the cooling loads (e.g., zones 1B, 2A, and 3A).

Fig. 10b shows the same analysis for the annual total loads but normalized by the performances of the baseline models. The highest saving of 11.74% is achieved for climate 5A, while the lowest relative saving of 2.26% is obtained for climate 1B. Here, it is worth noting that by relatively expressing the results, the savings can indicate the opposite than if they are expressed in absolute terms in some climate regions. For example, the relative saving achieved in climate region 7 (7.87%) is higher than for zone 8 (3.73%), while the absolute saving attained in climate 8 is slightly higher than in zone 7, i.e., 1.88 kWh/m² against 1.77 kWh/m². Based on this observation, it can be concluded that using relative savings (which are commonly used) could hide the real effectiveness of PCMs in buildings if the absolute difference is not simultaneously provided.

To a deeper understanding, the corresponding savings for heating and cooling loads of the analyzed designs are shown in Fig. 10c and Fig. 10d. Regarding the heating load savings, the performance of PCMs in the cold climates is similar (i.e., zones 6A, 7, and 8), reducing between 0.53-0.65 kWh/m². The best heating load saving of 1.72 kWh/m² is obtained for climate 5A. In this zone, there are considerable annual heating loads, but the cooling loads are dominant for the climate and building analyzed. This indicates that the effectiveness of PCMs for reducing heating loads improves under these conditions, and this is because during the cold seasons there is more “extra” heat available to be stored in the PCMs, which improves their heating effectiveness. This analysis is also observed in the relative heating savings, where 19.13% and 22.26% savings are achieved in climates 4A and 5A, respectively. Furthermore, all the small heating loads can be reduced to zero in hot climates as shown in Fig. 8d and Fig. 8g for climates 2A and 3A.

Regarding the cooling load savings, reductions between 1.03-1.62 kWh/m² are achieved for the different climates, and the best performance of PCMs is attained in climate 2A. The largest relative savings are obtained for the cold regions, reaching the highest saving of 21.45% in climate zone 7. There is a common pattern observed in cold climate zones; the higher component saved (cooling)

is the opposite of the dominant loads. This is, the higher components saved for zones 6A, 7, and 8 are the cooling loads, but the heating loads are dominant in these climates. Thus, the effectiveness of PCMs for reducing the cooling loads improves in these climates because they can easily release the heat stored and achieve more number of days with a complete cycle of charge/discharge.

Fig. 10: Annual load savings for the buildings using the optimal PCMs compared to the baseline models in the different climate zones analyzed.

3.5. Summary and discussion about the optimal designs

This section summarizes and discusses the optimized designs obtained for each climate zone analyzed. Fig. 11 shows the optimal melting temperatures and thicknesses for the three PCM layers in each climate zone, and for three specific sets of solutions: the best designs obtained for reducing the annual total loads are shown in Figs. 11a-b; the best designs obtained for reducing the annual heating loads (Opt-1) are shown in Figs. 11c-d, and the best designs obtained for reducing the annual cooling loads (Opt-48) are shown in Figs. 11e-f.

Regarding the melting temperatures of PCMs, the optimal designs indicate that these have to be set with different values for each PCM layer. This conclusion is observed for all the studied climate zones and the three specific designs (total loads, heating loads, and cooling loads), see Fig. 11a, Fig. 11c, and Fig. 11e. Even in climate zone 1B where the cooling loads are extremely dominant, PCMs with different melting temperatures work better. Here, it is worth remembering that climates 1B and 2A have a single optimal solution, so the results of the best designs for total loads, heating loads, and cooling loads are the same. Thus, these results demonstrate that using several PCMs with different melting temperatures is preferred instead of a single melting temperature.

As to the optimal PCM melting temperatures for each climate, high values and nearby to the HVAC temperature setpoint for cooling are optimum in climates with only cooling loads, such as zones 1B and 2A. The optimal melting temperature for the PCM-1 (external walls) shows to be highly sensitive to the dominant load. This is, the optimal values strongly vary between the designs for reducing the total loads, heating loads, or cooling loads, e.g., in zone 3A. Also, the optimal values strongly vary between the different climate zones for the same target design. A quite clear pattern is observed for the optimal melting temperatures of the PCM-2 (internal walls) and PCM-3 (ceilings); both have similar variation rates regarding the climate zone, and the optimal melting of PCM-2 is higher than the PCM-3. Furthermore, this pattern is observed for the three specific designs analyzed.

Regarding the optimal thickness of the PCM layers, a pattern is observed for the PCM-2 (internal walls); the thickness should be carefully designed and thin layers between $\simeq 5\text{-}13$ mm are preferred for hot climate zones with high dominance of cooling loads, such as zones 1B, 2A, and 3A. The reason for this pattern along with the high melting temperatures (relative) discussed before for the PCM-2 could be because this PCM layer is located in the internal walls. So, the storing of more heat by using a thicker layer of PCM cannot be properly evacuated in a fully passive way from the studied building in hot climates, resulting in a lower effectiveness of this PCM layer. Another common observation derived from the optimal thicknesses obtained is that if both loads are present (heating and cooling) and if the melting temperatures are the optimal ones, it is possible to add large quantities of PCMs without worsening the performance of the building. This is found for the climates zones 4A, 5A, 6A, 7, and 8, where the optimal thicknesses are the maximum allowed.

Fig. 11: Summary of the optimization results for melting temperatures and thicknesses of the three PCMs in the different climate zones studied. (a)-(b) Best design for reducing the total loads; (c)-(d) Best design for reducing the heating loads; (e)-(f) Best design for reducing the cooling loads.

4. Conclusions

An optimization-based method to design passive latent energy storage using phase change materials (PCMs) with different melting temperatures in buildings was introduced. The main novelty of the present research is the proposal to use several PCMs with different melting temperatures instead of a single one, as well as a general method for their optimal design independent of the case study building and climate. For a deeper understanding of the physical performance of passive

PCMs in buildings, the optimization-based design was raised as a truly multi-objective problem to find the best trade-off between the ideal annual heating and cooling loads. Thus, the optimization-based method comprised the dynamical coupling of the multi-objective Non-dominated Sorting Genetic Algorithm-II (NSGA-II) with the EnergyPlus software. As a case study building, the small office from the prototype models of the DOE with the ASHRAE Standard 90.1–2019 was chosen. Three different PCMs were added to the ceiling and external and internal walls in the building. Parametric models of the PCMs were developed in EnergyPlus to simultaneously optimize the melting temperature and quantity of each PCM. To evaluate the energy performance of the building employing the proposed PCM approach in different climates, eight well-representative locations according to the ASHRAE 169-2020 climate classification and within the WMO Region VI (Europe) were selected. For this, a method to select the better-centered location of each climate zone was proposed and applied. Finally, an optimization-based design of PCMs was performed for each selected location.

The selected climate-representative locations are in close agreement with the centroids of climate zones of the ASHRAE 169-2020 classification. In addition to this, the baseline models showed logical values of annual loads for heating and cooling, which validated the representativeness of the selected locations. Thus, using the representative locations found for other studies to design or evaluate the performance of building technologies within the WMO Region VI (Europe) is recommended.

Different levels of complexity were found to achieve the optimal design of PCMs in the studied climate zones, which the optimization method proposed was able to address robustly. Furthermore, although the specific values of the optimal results for the melting temperatures and thicknesses can be related to the case study employed, important and general conclusions could be demonstrated, among them:

- Regardless of the climate zone analyzed, different melting temperatures for each of the three PCMs are preferred. This validates the potential for using several PCMs with different melting temperatures in buildings.
- The optimal melting temperatures of the PCMs placed in external walls are quite sensitive regarding the dominant loads. This is mainly noted in climates where both loads, heating and cooling, are present.
- In hot climates with only cooling loads (e.g., 1B and 2A), the optimal melting temperature of PCMs should be designed with similar values to the temperature setpoint for cooling to maximize its effectiveness. Moreover, in climates where both loads are present, a specific combination of melting temperatures of PCMs should be determined, but based on the pattern observed some general design guidelines can be drawn. For instance, regardless of the climate zone considered, the melting temperature of the PCMs placed in the internal components should be higher than the one of the PCMs placed in the ceilings.

- For climates where the heating and cooling loads are present, large quantities of PCM can be employed without worsening the performance of the building if the melting temperatures of PCMs are optimal. This was particularly noted for climate zones 4A, 5A, 6A, 7, and 8, where the optimal PCM thicknesses achieved were the maximum allowed.
- If only cooling loads are present, the PCMs should be incorporated into the envelope of the building (external walls and ceilings), and the PCM amount in the internal components has to be carefully designed. This was observed for climate zones 1B, 2A, and 3A where the optimal thicknesses achieved were thin layers ranging between 5-13 mm, while the maximum thickness allowed was chosen for PCMs placed in external walls and ceilings. The physical reason for this is that in hot climates, PCMs placed in the internal components cannot properly evacuate the heat daily stored because of the low-temperature variations, reducing its effectiveness. This effect has a lower impact on the envelope of the buildings because larger daily temperature variations are present and passive PCMs can improve their effectiveness.

Regarding the impact of the optimized PCMs on the performance of the buildings, the following conclusions can be remarked:

- The optimal designs can reduce between 1.53-2.75 kWh/m² of the annual total loads compared to the baseline models.
- The highest saving regarding the annual total loads of 11.74% was achieved in zone 5A, while the lowest one of 2.26% was obtained in zone 1B. Thus, the best performances of PCMs were achieved for climate zones where both heating and cooling loads were present, which is a common feature for most of the locations analyzed within the WMO Region VI (Europe). Moreover, the population (i.e., analyzed locations) is majorly in climate zones 5A and 4A (i.e., where the best PCM performances were found). Therefore, good potential for exploiting PCM-based technologies in Europe is proven.
- If both loads (heating and cooling) are present and with comparable values (no one is highly dominant), the effectiveness of PCMs is higher for reducing the lower loads. For instance, PCMs work better to reduce the cooling loads in a cold climate where the heating loads are dominant.
- For some cases, the analysis of the relative load savings can hide the real effectiveness of PCMs, i.e., a relative higher savings can exactly mean the opposite when it is expressed in absolute values. This highlighted the necessity to develop an effectiveness index for PCMs in buildings, which will be addressed in future works.

Finally, it is worth noting that the baseline models studied in this work were already high-performance designs. Moreover, the PCMs were evaluated as fully passive in the baseline models without an optimal combination with other passive or active strategies. Therefore, future works

also will focus on assessing the performance of several PCMs with different melting temperatures combined with other optimal passive strategies, as well as in other building typologies, such as single- and multi-family residential buildings.

Data availability

The results of the climate-representative locations selected within the WMO Region VI (Europe) can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7025795>.

For closer analysis (or their reproduction), the optimization results and the EnergyPlus models can be found at <http://dx.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7025809>.

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